

COLOUR: REVEALS YOUR PERSONALITY

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Abstract:

Colours are forces radiant energies that affect us positively or negatively, whether we are aware of it or not in our daily life. The effects of colours should be experienced and understood not only but also psychologically and symbolically. This paper investigates the various effects of light and colours on our visual apparatus –eye and brain and their anatomical relationships and functions. This paper describes the influence of colour radiation on our mind and spirit. Discovery of relationships, mediated by the eye and brain is major concern of my studies. Paper describes colour perception and colour aesthetic in three directions: 1) Impression (visually) 2) Expression (emotionally) 3) Construction (symbolically).

Keywords:

Colour, communication, Nature, psychological experience, Experience, Aesthetic.

So, are you ready for the interview, is everything there on tips, sure, confident! Here you are forgetting one thing. Have a look in the mirror before you step out. Is your dress also as updated as your knowledge is? Yes do not ignore it as you are being watched as minutely as you are judge. Is the colour of your dress suits the choice of the employer? Every different colour creates a certain effect on us emotionally. Such an effect of a colour on the mind and body is pleasing or irritating, relaxing or exciting, warm or cool, bright or dull. Because some colours stimulate our heartbeats and breathing. And some colours have an calming & refreshing effect on our nervous system.

Colour is a means of expressing one's individuality. Colour appeals to our senses and helps to express emotions and feelings. It makes our environment more joyful, pleasing and inspiring. It plays a very important role in our daily routine because we are surrounded by the colourful nature and man-made objects. We accept colour as naturally as we feel sunshine or shadow. So it is a vehicle of communication of our personality. Actually, colour is a sensation produced on the eye by the ray of decomposed light. Light is the source of colour. Absence of light means no indication of colour the colour of an object is the reflected part of light. For instance, when an object is blue, it means that the surface of the object has reflected blue colour and has absorbed all other colours. If a surface reflects all colours equally, we see white. When a surface absorbs all colours equally, we see black. Scientifically, white indicates presence of all colours while black means absence of all colours, physicists deal with light which is measurable entity as the source of colour. Chemists are concerned with pigments, which reflect the colour that we see. Physiologists regard colour as a sensation and how the eye perceives it. By psychologist delve into the mystery of how the brain interprets colours. Now doctors, psychiatrists and therapists use colours to heal the distressed and mentally challenged people.

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The actual sight of colour is a psychological experience, which reveals our unconscious desires, subtle emotions and must more. This parameter of language is fun to know the “true colour” of the people. And its certainly not very difficult for us to decide the language colours speak. Your favorite colour reveals a lot about your personality. Warm colour are associated with sunlight, summer flame and informality whereas cool colours create the effect of a result, soothing and a relaxing environment and are associated with the sky, ice, cold water, winter, shadow and formality. Therefore, every colour has a certain emotional effect on the mind and body which gives us the ability to read the personality of others as per the following: White is synonymous with purity and peace. The person liking this colour is a perfect idealist who favours white and is just a perfect combination of balance, purity and harmony. But they have their own share of troubles. It’s almost impossible for them to mix with all kinds of people. They seek someone is pure as themselves. People favoring black are perfect diplomats. He’ll want you do discover more about himself. We can never be sure of his reactions on anything we do. He conceals effortlessly. We can never accuse him of not telling anything about himself. There may not be anything about his part. Generally these types of people believe in the formality of life.

The colour of sun is perhaps the brightest among the colours. Yellow creates optimism in the personality and spreads gaiety and vivacity. It is more acceptance to young people. A person favoring yellow needs a patient partner. Who is never tired of showering affection, praise and gratitude? Dark yellow colour shows cool and balanced system of mind, which deals with all problems through practical ground. Person liking green colour may belong to the zodiac sign of Taurus or Virgo. They are loyal, trustworthy, and able to forgive and forget. They have a sympathetic ear for other’s problems. Green is the colour of nature and is preferred by mature people. They gain fame where they serve and get opportunities for promotion. They are renowned in their field of work.

Blue colour is preferred by loving people. These types of people do not show their love that is why such people do not succeed in their love life. They are sentimentalists. A blue shirt of your friend flashes the message that he demonstrates his love and loyalty for you. These types of people prefer to take gift and sweet. Even a red rose will do. Girls who like blue are loyal but don’t forget that they expect the same from you. Once you have breached their trust, only God can save you! Who does not know that red signifies the leader and winners? Red preferring people are over ambitious and firm decision makers. These people get excited very soon and give orders mercilessly to their subordinates. Dark red does not mean showing passion only but it also shows hatred and danger. You may achieve your goal due to your over ambitious nature. Remember the bouquet of red roses expressed the love towards the lover. It is agreed that red signifies love but in the physical sense of the word. In fact, such a person will hate every other person who looks at his girlfriend. These types of people fulfill every need to their beloved. Beloveds can always be sure that their love life can never be devoid of excitement. Those who like brown are the down to earth type. They feel that the best way of showing love and care is through material comforts and luxury. Financial security is uppermost in the minds of brownies. Yet these practical workers are touched by small gestures of help and kindness like a child.

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You'll find the loneliness in the eyes of pink preferring people but they are a rare blend of friend, lover and adviser. They prefer delicacy, softness and happiness in every moment of life. Generally pink colour is preferred by either a child or a female. Choice of colours is purely individual which shows the temperament of a person. So go out and discover more about people through their choices of colour.

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